

USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING CORRESPONDENT STUDENTS ENGLISH LANGUAGE COMPONENTS

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Abstract. *The article substantiates the importance of introducing interactive active teaching methods in the educational process. The main emphasis is is committed to teaching English to part-time students. The author underlined nods that it is not enough for a teacher of the new generation to be competent knowledgeable in their field of knowledge, it is necessary to use use methodological innovations that are currently associated using interactive teaching methods. The author considers a number interactive methods, the introduction of which will contribute to achieving achievement of the set goal - increasing the effectiveness of educational process, achieving high performance by all students.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, problem-based learning, discussion, training, brainstorming.*

At the present stage of development of society, knowledge of English becomes very important. There is no need to convince anyone of the need to learn a foreign language, life itself testifies to this. TV programs are broadcast in English, scientific literature is published, modern songs are played and foreign films are shown. In addition, instructions for various household appliances are written in English. In most cases, even if there is a translation, it is not always correct and therefore learning English is very relevant. But to make the language learning process more effective, you it is necessary to use interactive teaching methods. For a modern teacher, it is not enough to be competent in own field of knowledge, it is necessary to use introduce methodological innovations that today are associated with the changing interactive teaching methods. Interactive training based on direct interaction between students and their experiences his friends. The goal of interactive learning is to increase the effectiveness of learning a process in which all students achieve high results in teaching. Let us consider this problem using the example of teaching part-time students. Interactive learning involves immersion of correspondence students into a real-world business collaboration environment to solve problems with the goal of developing the necessary qualities of a future specialist. All participants votive process interact with each other, exchange information, jointly solve problems and model the situation.

The use of interactive forms of training when working with students correspondence form has a number of advantages, namely:

- involving students in the learning process no longer as passive listeners, but as active participants;
- increasing the motivation of this category of students to study the subject;
- mastering modern technical teaching aids;
- formation and development of independent work skills in searching for information and productive use of acquired knowledge in practice.

It should be noted that the educational process with correspondence students new form of education, based on the use of interactive technology, aims to involve all students in the educational process regardless of their language level. Cooperative activity means that all participants exchange information and ideas. During the lesson, an atmosphere of free

communication is created, which is characteristic is developed by cooperation between participants in the educational process, balance of arguments, accumulation of general knowledge, fair assessment and mutual control. Let's consider a number of interactive teaching methods, the introduction of which will help achieve this goal - increasing the effectiveness of educational process and achieving results for all students. Group discussions are usually held on a specific topic and is aimed at finding the right solution and achieving the best mutual understanding. Group discussions promote better learning the material being studied. At the first stage of group discussion, part-time students are given task for a certain time, during which they must prepare provide a reasoned, detailed answer. During the discussion, participants should discuss the problems of public personally or freely exchange knowledge, opinions, ideas on controversial questions. Its essential feature is the combination of dialogue-talk judgments and disputes-clash of different points of view and positions. Discussion is student-centered learning. It is characteristic is enhanced by the active interaction of students with each other and intensive meaningful, personality-oriented training on the part of the teacher. The benefit of the discussion is that it shows how well the group understands this problem. The advantage of the discussion is that the discussion during short period of time (and the number of hours for correspondence students is limited) gives the ability for the teacher to model real problems, develop students' ability to listen and share their thoughts, interact and analyze the real situation, separate the important from the unimportant.

Thus, the discussion provides an opportunity to understand and appreciate the many variety of existing views on any problem, conduct a thorough analysis of each of them, having heard the individual opinion of each participant in the discussion on this topic. This form of working with students is correspondence students is very important and productive, since during the discussion and they acquire the communication skills they need for long-term professional development.

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